

- [Support](#)

Edvander Pires ▾

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Statistics of downloads and reproductions from a previous platform #10654

Status

Resolved

Department

Podcast management

THIS REQUEST IS FOR

Pro subscription (Projeto Cocriando)**Purchased:** 05/20/2023 **Expires:** 11/01/2023

Responses

You

Account Owner

May 22

Dear managers,

I have created my account on Podcastics and I made the migration of the Plurissaberes Podcast. However, I have not seen the statistics of downloads and reproductions from the previous platform yet: the PodCloud. After migrating, have I lost all those data?

Thanks in advance.

Podcastics • Tech

Staff

May 22

Hi Francisco,

Thank you for your message, and welcome to Podcastics ! ☀️

When migrating to another podcast host, you will keep your statistics on the listening platforms websites, such as *Apple Podcasts Connect*, *Spotify for Podcasters*, *Google Podcasts Manager*...

However, please note that you will no longer have access to the statistics provided by your former host. We therefore advise you to save them (for example with screenshots or in data files).

Podcastics will not be able to import them back into your new interface, as each host has different technical standards; moreover, Podcastics respects the IAB international standard, which is not necessarily the case for PodCloud.

We remain at your entire disposal to help you with your migration.

If you need additional information, please do not hesitate to ask us!

First of all, I see that you have successfully imported your PodCloud RSS feed.

Congratulations! It's already a very good job; your episodes are now present in Podcastics.

Podcastics will support you every step of the way of your migration 😊

- You have now access to your Podcastics interface. I invite you to **check all the information** of your podcast (texts, episodes...). Podcastics indeed offers infinitely more options than PodCloud, and you can enhance your descriptions with **rich text, images, videos**, emojis...
- Do not hesitate to look around the Podcastics interface: this will allow you to familiarize yourself with the platform, but also to check that all the parameters of your podcast and its episodes are correct.
Don't be afraid to make changes! At the moment, Podcastics is not yet officially your new host. Also, none of the changes you make so far will be transmitted to your listeners. You can therefore **test everything you want**, without any risk for your podcast!
- When you feel that **your podcast is ready** for the big leap, then go to the « **Distribute** » tab of your Podcastics interface.
It will allow you to **transfer your RSS feed from PodCloud to Podcastics**.
The purpose of this operation is twofold: to inform the listening platforms that you have modified your RSS feed (so that they update correctly), and to ask PodCloud to redirect your old RSS feed to your new Podcastics feed.
For this, Podcastics offers you detailed wizards, which will guide you step by step.
 - Start with the **blue box**, which invites you to ask PodCloud to **redirect your RSS feed**. This is very simple, just follow the wizard steps.
 - Then, for each distribution platform (Apple Podcasts, Google Podcasts, Spotify, Deezer...), click on the « **Distribute to...** » button.
Again, wizards will guide you step by step; you will see, it is very easy, you just have to **follow each step carefully**.
 - Depending on the listening platforms (Apple, Spotify...), the update time will vary, it generally takes a few hours.
 - Once this is done: **congratulations!** You will have **completed your migration to Podcastics**.
Going forward, any changes you make to Podcastics will be reflected on listening platforms.
 - We advise you to keep your subscription with PodCloud for a few days, so that all your subscribers are redirected to Podcastics.

You will gradually discover that **many features** are available to you, such as **episode scheduling, episode notes** with **videos** and **images**, **file sharing, comments, reviews, ratings**, your **private messaging**, the customization of your **audio players** and your **website**, your **magic links**, your **QR Codes, unlimited user permissions** for teamwork, or **series of episodes** to group them according to their themes...

In short, a comprehensive toolbox to better manage your podcast, and make it even more attractive 😊

In addition, you will be able to consult your statistics, which offer you a lot of information, and in particular the « **heat map** », which will gradually fill in to give you the « life » of your podcast over the week.

When you release new episodes, you'll also find a tool for **comparing their launch performance**: it's a graph that compares their first week's listens, after they were released. This is very practical information to know which episodes have made the best starts.

As you get to grips with Podcastics, you will also be able to discover **usage tips** that will save you time, such as **duplicating episodes**, allowing you in one click to publish an episode that resumes all the information from a past episode (without having to re-enter everything), or even, for example, displaying your Twitter feed on your Podcastics website.

There are dozens of features waiting for you! 😊

Do not hesitate to test Podcastics; you benefit from a free month without any commitment (we do not ask you for your credit card). You are therefore free to test the platform as you see fit.

We remain at your disposal to assist you in these steps. If you need help, don't hesitate to ask us!

You can contact us at any time from your **support interface**:

<https://www.podcastics.com/support/>

You will find there the history of all your requests and previous messages.

Thank you,
Kind regards,

--

Nicolas

Podcastics Support - Podcast management

podcast@support.podcastics.com

You

Account Owner

May 22

Thank you so much for all these information, Nicolas! Please, call me Edvander or just Ed 😊

I work as a librarian in Brazil, more specifically in an academic library at Federal University of Ceará. Since I finished my Master's degree, in 2018, I have worked at managing podcasts focusing on themes to the Higher Education. In this respect, may I manage four podcasts at the same account on Podcastics?

After the trial month, I will decide to keep my subscription in the PRO plan. By the other hand, my subscription on PodCloud will finish in the beginning of July.

I need to advise you that the Plurissaberes Podcast will have its name changed between July and August. There will be a special episode about this changing.

Thank you once more,

Kind regards,

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Edvander Pires

Podcastics • Tech

Staff

May 23

Hi Edvander Ed 😊,

Thank you for your reply! ☀️

It's an honor to be able to host your podcast; we are happy to discover all that you have produced! Regarding the change of your podcast name, it is indeed best to do it after you have migrated your podcast.

This will prevent the listening platforms from being lost during the migration process.

With your Podcastics account, you can manage as many podcasts as you want. However, each podcast has its own subscription; this means that if you want to manage multiple podcasts, then you would have to subscribe to as many subscriptions. Each subscription can be the plan of your choice: Free, Premium, Pro or Max.

This is how many podcasts hosts work, and it allows us to offer the lowest prices on the market, including unlimited hosting, without any storage space restrictions, for only \$8 per month.

In addition, from 3 subscriptions, you automatically benefit from a 10% discount on all your subscriptions (at an equivalent or lower price).

For instance, a « Pro » subscription with unlimited hosting would then be only \$7.20 / month.

I hope this answers your question! If you need any additional information, please let us know: we're here to help!

Thank you,
Kind regards,

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Nicolas
Podcastics Support - Podcast management
podcast@support.podcastics.com

You

Account Owner

May 25

Thank you for your reply, Nicolas!

Just one more information:

I used to speech and write about library and podcast based on PodCloud. May I do the same based on Podcastics? If I may, is there any material that presents the historical and development of Podcastics? In this respect, I saw the account on Twitter was created in 2017 (fr) and 2019 (en). However, I think the platform and its services were founded before those years, am I correct?

Podcastics • Tech

Staff

May 25

Hi Ed,

Thank you for your reply! ☀️

Podcastics is part of a French company based in Paris and created in 2007.

Originally, the activity of the company was based on the provision of web services (sites, communities, platforms).

We created our first podcasts in 2007, and some still exist today.

Over the years, we have developed our recording studio to offer this service to our customers. So we started developing tools dedicated to podcasts, including statistics and audio players. At the time, these tools were only intended for our customers.

These tools have gradually been enriched; in 2018, we decided to create a platform for the general public, accessible to everyone.

Podcastics - whose name is the contraction of Podcast and Analytics - was therefore launched publicly in June 2019, and has since been aimed at podcasters around the world.

I hope this answers your question!

If you need additional information, please let us know 😊

Thank you,
Kind regards,

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Nicolas
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podcast@support.podcastics.com

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